

The Influence of Video Tutorials on Learning Outcomes of Islamic Religion in Class X Students in Online Business and Marketing Smk Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang

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ABSTRACT

This use method quantitative And type study experiment which aim For test influence video tutorial on the learning outcomes of Islamic Religion for class X Online Business and Marketing SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang. Population research, namely all Class X Online Business and Marketing SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang and the sample taken was 37 people class X Online Business and Marketing students at SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang and use Arikunto's opinion. Variable on study this there is 2, which first that is variable free that is the effect of using video tutorials (x) and the two dependent variables namely Islamic Religion learning outcomes for Class X students of Online Business and marketing at SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang (y). This research was conducted at SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang. Based on the results of data analysis, it was obtained that the value of $X = 86.5 >$ the value of $Y = 54.05$ so that it can be seen that there is influence Video tutorial on learning outcomes of Islamic Religion for Class X students of Online Business and Marketing at SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang. Results study This concluded that there is Influence Video tutorial on learning outcomes of Islamic Religion for Class X students of Online Business and Marketing at SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang. Matter This show that hypothesis Work Which state There is Influence Video tutorial on learning outcomes of Islamic Religion Class X Students Online Business and Marketing SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang, accepted.

INTRODUCTION

Language is a very important role in human life and is very supportive of continuity Education comes from the word didi, meaning bina, which means the nature of the act of fostering or training, or teaching and educating itself, thus, education is coaching, training, teaching, and all things that are part of the human effort to improve intelligence and skills. Education is a process of developing humans physically and spiritually, meaning every effort and effort to improve the intelligence of students. (Santoso 2019).

System education moment This experience change Which very fast. This change aims to improve the current education system. Various approach new has introduced And used For make learning more effective And meaning. Technology is Wrong One the most important factor in changing the education system. With technology learning become more efficient and effective (Santoso 2019).

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the education system national (Sisdiknas) Which meant with education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning environment and process learning so that participant educate in a manner active develop profession himself For own strength spiritual religious, control self, personality, intelligence, morals glorious, as well as Skills Which needed himself, public, nation And country (Bagunda 2020).

Based on the results of initial observations of the problems faced by students Class X Online Business and Marketing SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang in the teaching and learning process of Islamic religious subjects still uses materials Print teaching is in the form of printed books and uses more of the lecture method learning like This not enough give instruction on process search, understanding, discovery and application as well as causing students to be less active and even bored learning as a result, learning is less motivating as well can generate learning outcomes Which decrease.

As for media learning Which appropriate Which can increase Skills And ability think as well as Study independent Which can improve student learning outcomes , namely video tutorials . Video tutorials are _ study guide for national education purposes, these aspects are mandatory in Pay attention so that the learning process is not only focused on understanding students, but can also be applied in everyday life because on basically education no just process transfer knowledge However Also transfer moral values and kindness .Education religion Islam is business aware Which done educator in framework prepare participant educate For believes, understand, And practicing Islamic teachings through guidance, teaching or training activities Which has determined For reach objective Which has set.

METHODOLOGY

Type study Which applied on research This is quantitative. According to (Sugiyono, 2013: 7) method study quantitative is method scientific because it fulfills scientific principles, namely concrete, objective, measurable, rational And systematic. To get the results of this study, it is better first make design

from researcher to an Which will done. Design study Which carried out is the experimental design. The following is an overview of the implementation of this research explained in a simple table following :

Table 1. Implementation of this Research Explained

Treatment Group
1 Experiment X
2 Controls -

Information :

X: There is no treatment in the experimental class using video tutorials

- : There is no treatment in the control class using video tutorials

Research Variable

There is 2 type variable Which used in study This, that is as following :

1. Influence use videos tutorials moment process Study teach (variable free) with the X symbol
2. Results Study Religion Islamic students (variable bound) with symbol Y

Collecting Data

The population is the generalization area which consists of objects or subjects Which have quality And characteristic certain Which has set by researchers to study it and draw conclusions from it (Sugiyono, 2013:80). The population in this study were all students in class X Online Business and Marketing at SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang.

The sample is part or representative of the population studied According to (Arikunto, 2017: 173) . If the subject is less than 100 people, it is best to take all of them so that the research is a population study. Furthermore, if the number of subjects is more than 100 people, it can be taken between 10-15% or 20-25% or more. Because the population is relatively small, all populations are used as samples, with the term population sample or total sample, namely 37 people, 18 experimental people and 19 control people.

Technique collect that data used on study this is:

Documentation

Documentation technique is a data collection technique through written material Which containing data or information about something (Usman and Sakkir 2020). Technique documentation give information about the number of students in class X Online Business and Marketing SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang year lesson 2022/2023.

Test

This technique is used to obtain data about achievement student after activity Study teach held. As for test used is test written Which must done by every good student on group experiment nor on group control (Usman and Sakkir 2020). Test technique is used to measure learning outcomes of subject A religion of Islam for students in class X Business Online And Marketing SMK Country 2 Sidenreng Rappang. On At the end of learning, a test is carried out whose purpose is to see learning outcomes student. Test what is meant is giving questions in the form of multiple choice questions with a total of 30 items and consisting of 4 choice that is A, B, C And D use _ For find out the results Study student.

In technique This, data Which collected analyzed with technique statistics mean . Regarding the data analysis steps this is the acquisition of the test students are used to determine the classification of student scores. Acquired test converted become value in the formula below this:

$$N = \frac{SP}{SM} \times 100$$

Information :

- N : Student Score
- SP : Gain Score
- SM : Maximum Score
- 100 : Standard Score

Mean Formula Analysis

For know is use v ideo tutorial _ influential on the learning outcomes of Islamic Religion students in class X Online Business and Marketing at SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang, so formula is used means as follows:

$$M_x = (\sum F_x) / N_x \qquad m_y = (\sum F_y) / N_y$$

Information :

- M x = The average value of the experimental group
- $\sum f_x$ = Sum of experimental group values
- N x = Number of students in the experimental group
- M y = Average value of the control group
- $\sum f_y$ = Total value of the control group
- N y = Number of students in the control group

RESULTS

Study held in class X BDP SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang. The sample was taken from the entire population. In this research will be divided become 2 group that is group experiment Where in process learning will use media tutorial videos and group control Where in process activity learning No using video tutorials or use learning conventional. After do process learning second the group is given test.

Presentation Data

From results study Which done with use documentation and multiple choice tests as data collection instruments, so the following results are obtained:

- a. Data variable X, is data results Study Islam Which use media video tutorials (Group experiment).
- b. Data variable Y, is data results Study Islam Which using learning conventional (Control Group).

To facilitate the process of data analysis, the data that has been collected will be presented first and then analyzed, then proceed with hypothesis testing with statistical techniques as follows:

Table 2. Scores and Scores of the Experimental Group

No	Sample Code	Score	Mark
1	AMF	24	80
2	AH	26	86
3	GA	27	90
4	IBM	24	80
5	IK	26	86
6	I	24	80
7	MM	26	86
8	MFH	27	90
9	FOLDER	26	86
10	MA	26	86
11	MMS	27	90
12	M N	27	90
13	MNHN	26	86
14	MA	27	90
15	MD	28	93
16	N	26	86
17	S	26	86
18	S	26	86

From the results of studying Islam in the experimental group above, it shows that there were no students who scored 100. The highest score was 93 Then lowest value 80.

Table 3. Scores and Results of the Control Group

No	Sample Code	Score	Mark
1	A	23	76
2	AD	19	63
3	ARI	23	76
4	A	23	76
5	AI	18	60
6	H	23	76
7	HHL	23	76
8	IMP	19	63
9	I	23	76
10	MAA	21	70
11	MRFK	20	66
12	MAA	21	70
13	MF	23	76
14	MF	19	63
15	MI	19	63
16	MRR	23	76
17	N	21	70
18	Data Source: Test Results		73
19	RBR	21	70

Based on table 3 of the control group above, the highest value is obtained is 76 and the lowest score is 60. From the results of studying Islam in experiment and groups will control collected on following table:

Table 4. Results Study Group Experiment and Group Control

No	Mark	Experiment Group	Control Group
1	93	1	-
2	90	5	-
3	86	9	-
4	80	3	-
5	76	-	8
6	73	-	1
7	70	-	4
8	66	-	1
9	65	-	4
10	60	-	1
		18	19

Data Source: Test Results

Data Analysis

For know There is nope influence use media video tutorials to results Study Islam class X BDP SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang. From data Which has processed on table on so will analyzed in table calculation work means as follows:

Table 5. Work Mean Calculation

Group Experiment				Group Control		
fx 2	Fx	F	X/Y	F	Fy	fy 2
8,649	93	1	93	-	-	-
40,500	450	5	90	-	-	-
66,564	774	9	86	-	-	-
19,200	240	3	80	-	-	-
-	-	-	76	8	160	12,160
-	-	-	73	1	77	5,621
-	-	-	70	4	210	14,700
-	-	-	66	1	268	17,688
-	-	-	63	4	252	15,876
-	-	-	60	1	60	3,600
134,913	1,557	18		19	1027	69,645

Source Data : Processed From table 5

Means group experiment (X) and groups control (y) with formula :

$$Mx = \frac{1557}{18} = 86,5$$

$$my = \frac{1027}{19} = 54,05$$

DISCUSSION

This research was conducted with the intention to determine the influence of media-based learning video tutorials on learning outcomes in the subject of Islamic Religion class X Online Business and Marketing at SMK Negeri 2 Si denreng Rappang . The location for the implementation of this research was at State Vocational School 2 Si denreng Rappang by taking a sample of 37 students. In determining the distribution of the experimental and control groups by dividing based on predetermined classes .

Based on the scores obtained in this study, it shows that the differences in Islamic learning outcomes for students in class X BDP 1 and X BDP 2 at SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang who use video tutorials in the learning process are better than students who do conventional learning processes. Learning outcomes can be seen from the comparison of the results of the tests that have been carried out on students at the end of the learning process.

Result of experimental group using video tutorials in the learning process obtained a higher score compared to the control group which did not use video tutorials during the learning process. This can be seen from the results of the data analysis that was carried out showing the average value of the experimental group ($M_x = 86.5$) while the control group ($M_y = 54.05$). This value indicates that the value of M_x is greater than M_y ($86.5 \geq 54.05$).

Based on the gains obtained in the statement above, the hypothesis states that there is an effect of using video tutorials on the learning outcomes of Islamic Religion in class X Marketing Online Business SMK Negeri 2 Si denreng Rappang "accepted". As a consequence of this acceptance, the hypothesis states that there is no effect of the use of video tutorials on the learning outcomes of Islamic Religion in class X Online Business and Marketing at SMK Negeri 2 Si denreng Rappang "rejected".

Thus it can be concluded that the use of video tutorials in the learning process can have a positive influence. This is demonstrated using a video tutorial in the learning process on student learning outcomes is quite satisfactory compared to learning outcomes that do not use video tutorials on the learning process.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research on the effect of video tutorials on Islamic learning outcomes for class X students of Online Business and Marketing at SMK Negeri 2 Si denreng Rappang, it can be concluded as follows: Use video tutorials in the teaching and learning process have an influence on the learning outcomes of Islamic Religion in class X Online Business and Marketing at SMK Negeri 2 Si denreng Rappang. Based on the results of this study which have been analyzed, an average value of $M_x = 86.5 > M_y = 54.05$ is obtained and the results of the average value are found to indicate that there is an effect of using video tutorials on student learning outcomes in Islamic Religion. X Online Business and Marketing SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang. The final results show that students who learn using video tutorials have a positive impact compared to students who study as usual. For student It is hoped that they can play an active role in the teaching and learning process and in discipline, especially in the use of video tutorials so that learning activities are more interesting and more information is obtained. For teachers. Tutorial video learning media in the subject of Islamic Religion is an example of variation in learning media, therefore teachers can reuse or develop again with different material. For school It can be used as a means of helping and supporting teachers in the teaching and learning process as well as providing appreciation and motivation to teachers who are innovative in using learning media to facilitate learning and have a major influence on student learning outcomes. For further research. The results of this study are expected to be developed to increase maximum results in the use of media video tutorials on the activities of the teaching and learning process of Islam.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "The Influence of Video Tutorials on Learning Outcomes of Islamic Religion in Class X Students in Online Business and Marketing Smk Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang."

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